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of, Teatralna Sq., 2, Chernivtsi, Ukraine, 58002<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15494738>**CURRENT ISSUES AND MODERN VIEWS ON THE COURSE AND PREVALENCE OF OF HAEMORRHAGIC VASCULITIS IN CHILDREN: A LITERATURE REVIEW****Abstract.**

Haemorrhagic vasculitis, known as Schönlein-Genoch purpura, and also known as capillary toxicity, IgA-associated vasculitis, belongs to the group of primary systemic vasculitis, which is characterised by the involvement of mainly small-calibre vessels. [1] The etiological factors are diverse and not fully understood, but exposure to allergens, infectious factors, hypothermia, and trauma play a crucial role in its development. According to the results of current studies, the epidemiology of this disease varies considerably both geographically and climatically and has differences depending on age and gender. [4,5,6]

The purpose of the study is to investigate the etiological features of the course and prevalence of Shenehlein-Genoch vasculitis based on a review of scientific and current literature. The information was collected in Google Scholar, PubMed, Google Academy for the period 2015-2024. [8,9,10] In Ukraine, this disease occurs with a frequency of 10-20 cases per 100,000 children, and in recent years, according to statistics, there has been a slight upward trend. [1]

Keywords: haemorrhagic vasculitis, children, population

Etiology.

Haemorrhagic vasculitis is a disease with immune system dysfunction caused by acute perivascular deposition of immunoglobulin A (IgA) and neutrophil activation, characterised by skin lesions with the formation of cutaneous vasculitis, arthritis, and possible renal and gastrointestinal damage. [2] Rarely, the lungs or central nervous system (CNS) may also be affected. [3] Potential activators of the disease include a variety of infectious and non-infectious pathogens, the former including β -haemolytic streptococcus group A, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, *Bartonella henselae*, *Yersinia intercolitica*, viral factors, parasitic infestations, household, food allergens, insect bites, food allergens, medications, sometimes trauma, hypothermia or overheating, violations and non-compliance with the vaccination schedule. [5] Purpura is most common in children under the age of 10. According to the latest scientific data, among the age group: 60% of patients are aged 4-6 years, 30% of patients are under 10 years old. The incidence among boys is 5 times higher than in the opposite sex. [9,10,11,12] Taking into account the studies conducted in 2015-2019, a seasonal correlation was found between an increase in the incidence of the disease in the autumn-winter season among the paediatric population, but exacerbations of the disease in the summer season, namely against the background of rotavirus or

adenovirus infections, are not excluded. [11,12] Recent modern research materials in the search literature emphasise the significant influence of genetic triggers in the development of haemorrhagic vasculitis, in particular, studies conducted at the genome level have shown the effect of mutation on the progression of susceptibility to Schoenlein-Genoch purpura and the development of clinical complications, namely nephritis. [6,7,8]

Pathogenesis.

Due to the action of certain triggers and activation of hyperergic immune response, immunoglobulin A (IgA) complexes and complement component 3 (C3) first begin to be intensively deposited on small-calibre vessels, namely arterioles, capillaries and venules. [4] IgA aggregates or IgA complexes are actively deposited in target organs, which leads to the production of inflammatory mediators, involving prostaglandins, namely prostacyclin, which further stimulate the development of certain clinical manifestations. [13] The pathogenetic forms are the basic form of haemorrhagic vasculitis without an increase in the level of immune complexes in plasma and with an increase in the level of immune complexes in plasma. [15] The next form is the necrotic form, namely with cryoglobulinaemia. The main diagnostic criteria are the presence of palpable purpura and, in parallel, one of the following signs, namely diffuse abdominal pain, arthralgia or arthritis,

clinical or biochemical changes characteristic of renal damage, such as haematuria or proteinuria. [10] These characteristics for defining diagnostic criteria were proposed in 2006 by the European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) and the Paediatric Rheumatology Society (P.R.S.). [1]

Clinic and manifestations.

Analysing the statistical data of the 2022 study, the average age of patients was 4-6 years, however, the younger the child, the more severe clinical manifestations were recorded, indicating a direct correlation between age and the course of the disease. [1,2] Children under 4 years of age were more likely to be prescribed steroid replacement therapy compared to older children. Statistical data also indicate a direct correlation between sex, namely a predominance in the progression of the disease among boys (65%). [1]

The onset of the disease is acute, the manifestation is accompanied by a correlation of fever and the simultaneous appearance of the first skin manifestations, in the form of purpura on the feet, legs, buttocks, upper extremities, trunk, and head. [2] The rash is haemorrhagic, significantly elevated above the skin surface, does not disappear with pressure, is associated with itching, necrosis may occur in the centre, and often swelling occurs. [2] The next step is joint involvement, the appearance of arthralgia or arthritis of the large joints of the lower (knee, ankle) and upper extremities. [3] These symptoms are accompanied by swelling and severe pain. If the vessels of the gastrointestinal tract are affected, bleeding may occur, accompanied by severe pain. [5] Abdominal pain increases significantly after eating, during emotional and physical stress, and even when changing body position. [7]

Much later, with a rapid manifestation of the disease, the kidneys are affected, leading to the development of glomerulonephritis. Lesions of the respiratory tract, namely the lungs, are rarely detected in the paediatric population. The manifestations may be associated with the appearance of cough, bloody sputum, shortness of breath, and the severity will, of course, directly correlate with the massiveness of vascular damage. [1]

Course.

Schönlein-Genoch vasculitis has a lightning-like form with an acute onset and involvement of all the target organs in the pathological process. In severe cases, the lightning form is characterised by haemorrhages in the brain substance and adrenal glands with the development of acute adrenal insufficiency (Waterhouse-Fredericksen syndrome). [9] This course is clinically unfavourable, as it involves the rapid development of trobohaemorrhagic complications. Other forms of vasculitis are acute, subacute and chronic forms of the disease. [11,12]

The latest clinical and statistical data record cases of recurrent course with exacerbation periods from 6 months to 1 year, but sometimes they can last up to several years. [12]

Age-related features.

Over the past 10 years, the frequency of disease progression among children and adults has been actively studied, namely, the incidence of haemorrhagic

vasculitis in adults is 1 in 10, which is 13-14 cases per 1,000,000 adults per year, the average age of patients in this sample is 50 years. [1] In adulthood, the correlation of the incidence of the disease among the sexes is the same, and there is no trend like in children. [3] In comparison, the disease is much more severe in the adult population than in children, with complications such as nephritis being diagnosed in 50-80% of adults and only 20-40% of children. [4] End-stage renal disease (ESRD) is diagnosed and verified in 10-20% of patients, while in the paediatric population it is 1%. [12]

Conclusions.

After analysing the scientific and statistical data and summarising the results, it should be noted that the incidence and prevalence of Schönlein-Genoch vasculitis in the paediatric population and in the adult population differs significantly depending on seasonal and age characteristics. [3] These studies demonstrate an unlikely dominance of the progression of the disease in boys (1.2-1.5:1.0). [6] An analysis of the professional literature has shown that among the clinical manifestations of haemorrhagic vasculitis in childhood, the most frequent and generally mandatory should be the presence of palpable haemorrhagic purpura, widespread abdominal pain, immunoglobulin A deposits in various organs and systems, and joint damage with manifestations of arthralgia or arthrosis. [5]

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